

Thiourea and its Organic Derivatives. Part III. Oxidimetric Determination with Diethylene Tetra-ammonium Sulphatocerate (DTS)

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Diethylene tetra-ammonium sulphatocerate (DTS) has been used as a redox reagent for visual and potentiometric determination of thiourea and its several alkyl and aryl derivatives in sulphuric acid medium. In visual methods, ferroin and amylose have been used as indicators.

The thioureas are oxidised to corresponding disulphides in sulphuric acid medium with a single electron change. These direct methods are simple, accurate, instantaneous, and widely applicable.

The only effort to quantitatively oxidise thiourea with ceric sulphate was made by Cuthill and Atkins¹ who oxidised it to urea and sulphuric acid with the oxidant. No systematic study has so far been made to estimate thiourea and its organic derivatives by oxidimetric methods. Singh *et al.*² have used iodine monochloride and iodine trichloride as redox reagents for determination of thiourea and its several alkyl and aryl derivatives.

In the present work, diethylene tetra-ammonium sulphatocerate, recommended by Singh and Singh³ as a primary standard in cerimetry, has been used as a redox reagent for the visual and potentiometric determination of thiourea and its alkyl and aryl derivatives by oxidising them to the corresponding disulphides in sulphuric acid medium. In the visual titrations, ferroin and amylose have been used as indicators. These direct methods are simple, accurate, instantaneous, and widely applicable.

EXPERIMENTAL

Diethylene tetra-ammonium sulphatocerate (DTS) was prepared by the method of Singh and Singh³. A standard (*N*/50) solution of the oxidant was prepared by dissolving 15.494 g. of the compound in 2*N*-H₂SO₄ and making the volume to 1 litre with the acid.

Ferroin Indicator Method.—A known weight (10 to 50 mg.) of each compound was taken in a titration flask; sufficient water and enough of H₂SO₄ to keep normality of the solution at 3*N* were added. One drop each of *M*/400 potassium iodate (catalyst) and ferroin (*M*/100) was added, the solution was cooled to room temperature, and titrated with standard (*N*/50) DTS till the colour of the solution changed from red to pale blue. The method gave accurate results in case of thiourea and its alkyl derivatives only.

1. *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1937, 56, 5T.
2. *This Journal*, 1962, 39, 211, 49C.
3. *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1956, 14, 109.

Amylose Indicator and Potentiometric Method.—A known weight (10 to 50 mg.) of each compound was taken in a titration flask. In case of thiourea and its alkyl derivatives, sufficient water and enough of H_2SO_4 to keep normality of the solution at $2N$ were added. Each aryl derivative of thiourea was dissolved in $18N-H_2SO_4$ (10 to 12 ml) and sufficient water (40 to 70 ml) was added to keep normality of the solution at 2.5 to $3.5 N$. 2% KI (0.1 to 0.2 ml) was added to the solution which was cooled to room temperature and titrated with standard ($N/50$) DTS. In visual titrations, 0.2 ml of 1% amylose was used as an indicator; the solution acquired a blue colour at the end point. In case of thiourea and its alkyl derivatives, chloroform was also used as an indicator which turned pink at the end point.

In potentiometric method, a platinum wire, immersed in the solution to be titrated, was used as an oxidation-reduction electrode, coupled with a saturated calomel electrode. The solution was kept stirred by a mechanical stirrer during titration. Progress of the reaction was studied with a Mullard potentiometer. At the equivalence point there was a sharp jump in potential in each titration. A series of potentiometric titrations was performed with different amounts of each compound. The potentiometric titrations, one for each compound, are represented by curves A to J in Fig. 1.

FIG. 1

From the volume of standard ($N/50$) DTS solution used, corresponding to the end point in each titration (visual and potentiometric), the amount of each compound was calculated. Some typical results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Compounds.	Ferroin indicator.		Amylose indicator.		Potentiometric.	
	Taken.	Found.	Taken.	Found.	Taken	Found.
$\text{NH}_2\text{CS.NH}_2$	0.0122 g. 0.0228	0.0122 g. 0.0228	0.0159 g. 0.0304	0.0152 g. 0.0304	0.0122 g. 0.0244	0.0122 g. 0.0244
$\text{CH}_3\text{NH.CS.NH}_2$	0.0090 0.0288	0.0090 0.0288	0.0144 0.0361	0.0144 0.0361	0.0108 0.0270	0.0108 0.0270
$\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{.NH.CS.NH}_2$	0.0104 0.0300	0.0104 0.0301	0.0146 0.0405	0.0146 0.0404	0.0201 0.0501	0.0201 0.0500
$(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH.NH.CS.NH}_2$	0.0120 0.0387	0.0120 0.0388	0.0117 0.0442	0.0117 0.0443	0.0247 0.0610	0.0248 0.0511
$\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{.CH}_2\text{.CH}_2\text{.NH.CS.NH}_2$	0.0152 0.0397	0.0152 0.0396	0.0231 0.0447	0.0221 0.0448	0.0147 0.0498	0.0147 0.0500
$\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{.CH}_2\text{.CH}_2\text{.CH}_2\text{.NH.CS.NH}_2$	0.0133 0.0387	0.0133 0.0388	0.0225 0.0400	0.0225 0.0401	0.0112 0.0442	0.0112 0.0442
<i>o</i> -(CH_3) $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{.NH.CS.NH}_2$			0.0145 0.0392	0.0145 0.0393	0.0197 0.0398	0.0197 0.0399
<i>p</i> -(CH_3) $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{.NH.CS.NH}_2$			0.0200 0.0400	0.0200 0.0400	0.0144 0.0432	0.0144 0.0434
<i>o</i> -(OCH_3) $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{.NH.CS.NH}_2$			0.0150 0.0394	0.0150 0.0395	0.0205 0.0481	0.0208 0.0483
<i>o</i> -(OC_2H_5) $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{.NH.CS.NH}_2$			0.0211 0.0398	0.0211 0.0399	0.0142 0.0332	0.0142 0.0333
<i>p</i> -(OC_2H_5) $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{.NH.CS.NH}_2$			0.0200 0.0448	0.0201 0.0448		

The results recorded above show that the listed compounds can be determined by titration with standard (*N*/50) diethylene tetra-ammonium sulphatocerate. Thiourea and its organic derivatives are oxidised by this oxidant to the corresponding disulphides in sulphuric acid medium.

(R = alkyl or aryl group).

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